

FAILURE ANALYSIS AND SIZE SCALING STUDY OF NOTCHED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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1 Introduction

This work presents failure analysis and size scaling study of double-notched $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ carbon/epoxy composite laminate. A numerical analysis approach based on material property degradation method (MPDM) and cohesive element (CE) method is illustrated for progressive damage analysis of double-notched composite laminates. The MPDM is used to model the intra-lamina failure whereas the cohesive elements are employed to account for the delamination at the interfaces. Various failure theories are integrated in the MPDM-CE approach including continuum damage mechanics criterion, micromechanics of failure and fracture mechanics based criteria. Experimental tests are first conducted on original double-notched $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate and subsequently on notch-size scaled $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ and ply-level scaled $[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_s$ laminates to obtain failure patterns and damage progression. Progressive failure analyses of the $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate and its scaled laminates are then performed by the MPDM-CE approach. Size scaling effects are experimentally and computationally investigated, which significantly reveals a trend in strength reduction of double-notched composites with increasing specimen size. All the predictions are compared with the experimental results and reasonably good agreement is observed.

2 Experiment setup and results of $[45/90-45/0]_s$ laminate, notch-size scaled $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ and ply-level scaled $[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_s$ laminates

Normal-size Carbon/Epoxy AS4/3501-6 specimens with $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ layup, notch-size scaled specimens with $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ layup and ply-level scaled specimens with $[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_s$ layup are tested in tension. The normal-size specimens have a gauge length of 100 mm excluding a gripping length

of 50 mm from each top and bottom of specimens. Two 60 degree V-notched with same size are made on both sides of the specimens, respectively, as shown in Figure 1. The width, notch length and thickness of the other two scales are listed in Table 1. The elastic properties for AS4/35001-6 composite material are reported in Table 2. Strain gauges (GFLA-3-50) are attached to both sides of notched specimens to measure the longitudinal strain of specimens during the tensile testing. A strain reader is connected by wires to the strain terminals to record the strain values. The tensile tests are carried out by the Shimadzu machine AG-25TB at a constant rate of displacement of 1 mm/min. Failure behaviors and patterns are recorded by camera during the tests. The results of critical displacements (u_{crit}) and failure load (F_{crit}) of the double-notched specimens with different scales are summarized in Table 3.

The experimental results of the notched specimens at different scales indicate that damage usually initiates at the notch roots, and all notched specimens exhibit typical brittle fracture with fiber breakage. Failures of the specimens are observed by the initiation and propagation of longitudinal cracks in $\pm 45^\circ$ and 0° plies running from the notch roots and transverse cracking in 45° and 90° plies followed by delamination at the interfaces and fiber failures in $\pm 45^\circ$ and 0° plies. The stress-strain responses of notched specimens show no significant nonlinearity from initial loading until final failure. No change on the failure mode between the normal-size $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ and scaled specimens is found.

Additionally, the experimental results of different scaled specimens show a trend in notched strength reduction of specimens with increasing size. The measured strength of the normal-size specimen is 368.9 MPa which is reduced by 15.65% due to

notch-size scaling and 37.18% in ply-level scaling effects. More extensive and significant delamination is seen to occur in the ply-level scaled specimens than in the notch-size scaled specimens (Figure 2).

3. Progressive failure analysis of notched [45/90-45/0]_s laminate and its scaled laminates

3.1 Methodology

A material property degradation scheme (MPDM) is applied to model the progressive failure of notched laminates. The idea of the MPDM is that a damage material can be described by an equivalent material with degraded material property or stiffness. In the stiffness degradation scheme by MPDM, the stiffness matrix of a failed element is effectively degraded to reflect the damage of the element. Two states of damage are considered: matrix failure (or partial failure) and fiber failure (or complete failure). When MPDM is used in the failure analysis, failure initiation in an element is usually determined by a failure criterion and progressive failure analysis will be carried out by the MPDM scheme. Several failure criteria are coupled with MPDM to indicate the intra-laminar damage including Tsai-Wu criterion [2], Christensen criterion [3], micromechanics of failure (MMF) [4] and continuum damage mechanics (CDM) [5]. Details of the criteria are highlighted in Table 4. For these criteria, notations such as longitudinal tensile strength X_T , compressive strength X_C , transverse tensile strength Y_T , compressive strength Y_C , and in-plane shear strength S_{12} , out-of-plane shear strength S_{23} are used. All of the four criteria have different modeling strategies for matrix-dominated and fiber-dominated modes. When Tsai-Wu, Christensen and MMF criteria are integrated with the MPDM to model the in-plane progressive failure, a complete stiffness degradation scheme is used to reflect the matrix or fiber failures (by using a degradation factor of 10^{-6}). The CDM criterion, on the other hand, can describe a gradual stiffness degradation of the failed elements due to matrix failure but a drastic stiffness drop due to fiber failure. With focus on improving the modeling of fiber failure, a modified scheme to traditional MPDM is introduced considering a fracture process in fiber failure. By this modified scheme, damage in fiber is allowed and a damaged fiber is able to bear additional load until ultimate failure. The modified scheme gradually degrades the stiffnesses of the failed elements by a degradation factor d_f ($d_f < 1$)

when fiber is damaged, and completely degrades fiber stiffness upon reaching ultimate failure ($d_f = 1$). The total energy dissipation by this fracture process can be equal to the fracture energy of the material and can be derived from the softening post-peak curve (Figure 2). If ε_0 is defined as the damage strain when fiber damage initiates and ε_f as critical strain when fiber is completely failed, with assuming a linear softening post-damage response, the damage variable d_f accounting for the linear degradation scheme of fiber can be expressed by:

$$d_f = 1 - \frac{\varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon_1} \cdot \frac{\varepsilon_f - \varepsilon_1}{\varepsilon_f - \varepsilon_0} \quad (1)$$

where

$$\varepsilon_0 = \frac{X_T}{E_l}, \quad \varepsilon_f = \frac{2G_{Ic}}{X_T l_e} \quad (2)$$

and X_T , E_l , G_{Ic} , l_e are composite longitudinal tensile strength, elastic modulus, fracture energy and characteristic length of the failed element, respectively. For simplicity, only the CDM and Christensen failure criteria are applied with the aforementioned fibre damage scheme and denoted as MCDM and MChristensen criteria, respectively.

For delamination modeling, cohesive element method is used adopting a quadratic stress based criterion to model delamination onset and an energy-based criterion to model delamination growth. The initiation of interface damage is controlled by one normal interface stress t_n and two shear interface stresses t_s and t_t , which can be written as:

$$\left(\frac{t_n}{S_n}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{t_s}{S_s}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{t_t}{S_t}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (3)$$

where S_n , S_s and S_t are the cohesive strengths.

For delamination propagation prediction, a fracture mechanics-based criterion is used:

$$\frac{G_n}{G_{Ic}} + \frac{G_s}{G_{IIc}} + \frac{G_t}{G_{IIIc}} = 1 \quad (4)$$

where G_n , G_s and G_t are the work done by the tractions and their relative displacements in the normal and shear directions, respectively; G_{Ic} , G_{IIc} and G_{IIIc} are the critical strain energy release rates (SERRs) corresponding to mode I, mode II and mode III fractures, respectively. All cohesive parameters are referred to Camanho and Davila [6] and given in Table 5.

The MPDM-CE approach and all failure criteria are coded into a user-defined material subroutine (UMAT), and failure analyses are carried out using the implicit solver of ABAQUS.

3.2 Finite Element Model

Finite element models for double-notched normal-size specimens with $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ layup and their scaled size are developed. The geometry and dimensions of the FE models are same as the specimens in the experiment. The boundary conditions and mesh of the FE models are shown in Figure 4. Because the laminate is symmetrical in thickness direction, only half-thickness laminate (4 plies for the $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate) is modeled with symmetrical boundary conditions. The FE models are built with 8-node three-dimensional continuum shell elements (SC8R) and 8-node hexahedral cohesive elements (COH3D8) inserted at the interfaces between plies, with one element in the thickness per ply. The cohesive elements connect adjacent plies by sharing nodes with the continuum shell elements, as shown in Figure 4(c). The modulus of the cohesive element is assumed 4.0 GPa and cohesive element thickness is 0.005 mm, which is approximately one twenty-fifth of the ply thickness. This thickness is referred to the recent work of Hallett and Wisnom [7,8] and it is found to give acceptably accurate results within reasonable computation time. If the thickness is chosen very small and close to zero, the computational time will be much longer and convergence is not guaranteed. In contrast, when the thickness is made bigger and close to the ply thickness, the results become less accurate.

3.3 Results

The predicted applied load vs. displacement curves of the $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate by the Tsai-Wu, Christensen, MMF, CDM, MCDM and MChristensen criteria are shown in Figure 5 and compared with the experimental data. There are discrepancies in the failure load predictions by different failure criteria in which the loads obtained by MCDM and MChristensen criteria are higher than others and closer to the experimental failure load. The highest ultimate loads by the MCDM and MChristensen criteria predict up to 84% and 90% of the experimental failure load, respectively. Since the predicted damage patterns, progression and

sequences by all failure criteria are quite similar, only the patterns predicted by MChristensen criterion are displayed here (Figure 6). At the early stage, short longitudinal splits are found to initiate from the notch roots in the 45° and 0° plies and matrix cracks are predicted in the 90° ply. The intermediate -45° ply which is affected by the damages from the 90° and 0° plies is also found with few matrix cracks and splits. On increasing the load application, longitudinal splits in $\pm 45^\circ$ plies and 0° ply begin to lengthen and matrix cracks begin to saturate in $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° plies. At the maximum load, additional splitting occurs toward the middle of the 0° ply and fiber failure initiates at the notch roots of the 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies. It is found that delamination also initiates at the interfaces by this stage. Shortly thereafter, fiber failures in the $\pm 45^\circ$ and 0° plies quickly spread across the entire width of the $\pm 45^\circ$ and 0° plies accompanied by extensive delamination at three interfaces, leading to the ultimate failure.

The predicted load vs. displacement curves for the notch-size and ply-level scaled laminates are presented in Figures 7 and 8, respectively. Only the damage patterns predicted by the MChristensen criterion for the notch-size and ply-level scaled laminates are shown in Figures 9 and 10 since the initiation and propagation of damage and sequences predicted by other criteria are quite similar to the MChristensen criteria. The failure mechanism and patterns for scaled laminates are similar to those of the normal-size $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate. All the transverse cracks at $\pm 45^\circ$ plies and 90° plies, splitting and fiber failure $\pm 45^\circ$ plies and 0° ply and delamination at these interfaces are predicted and agree with the experimental observation. Nevertheless, more delamination is predicted for the notch-size and ply-level scaled laminates than for the normal size laminate.

It is noted that the MCDM and MChristensen criteria predict better than other criteria for the two kinds of scaled laminates by considering the damaged fiber is able to sustain additional load until it is completely exhausted. Therefore, the major load drops predicted by the MCDM and MChristensen criteria are closer to the experimental load, as shown in Figures 7 and 8.

Table 6 summarizes the results of notch-size and ply-level scaling effects predicted by the six criteria, where the percentage of strength reduction is with

respect to the corresponding strength of the normal-size laminate. Extensive and significant delamination was observed in the scaled specimens, causing the notched strength of these laminates further reduced.

4. Conclusions

This paper presented the progressive failure and delamination analysis in scaled double-notched carbon/epoxy laminates by the MPDM-CE approach. The damage progression and failure patterns of the $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate with different scales were modeled with this approach. Various failure criteria such as the Tsai-Wu, Christensen, MMF, CDM, MCDM and MChristensen were presented in a comparative study. Of all the criteria, the MCDM and MChristensen criteria which take into consideration of the fracture process in fiber failure may provide better failure load predictions than others. The damage patterns and sequences predicted by different criteria were similar and agree reasonably well with the experimental observation.

In addition, a reduction in strength with increasing size observed in the experiment has been captured computationally. A similar amount of the strength reduction was obtained with the simulation from different failure criteria. It was also found that no significant change in the failure mechanism is observed between scaled laminates, except that more delamination was predicted.

The numerical simulation has shown that by describing a fracture process for fiber failure modeling, the MCDM and MChristensen criteria have improved the strength prediction of composites. Since there is no restriction made for the implementation of the fracture process to conventional models, the Tsai-Wu and MMF criteria therefore can be also modified to improve their predictions.

Fig. 1 Geometry and dimension of specimens

Table 1 Number and dimension value of specimens for different scales

Layup	Size type	No of specs	W (mm)	H (mm)	c (mm)
$[45/90/-45/0]_s$	Normal size	5	20	1	5
$[45/90/-45/0]_s$	Notch-size scaling	4	40	1	10
$[45_2/90_2/-45_2/0_2]_s$	Ply-level scaling	4	40	2	10

Table 2. Elastic properties of AS4/3501-6 composite system [1]

Material properties	Values
Longitudinal modulus E_1 (GPa)	147
Transverse moduli $E_2 = E_3$ (GPa)	10.3
In-plane shear moduli $G_{12} = G_{13}$ (GPa)	7.0
Shear modulus G_{23} (GPa)	3.7
In-plane Poisson's ratios $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	0.3
Poisson's ratio ν_{23}	0.5
Longitudinal tensile strength X_T (MPa)	2280
Longitudinal compressive strength X_C (MPa)	1725
Transverse tensile strength Y_T (MPa)	57
Transverse compressive strength Y_C (MPa)	228

In-plane shear strength $S_{12}=S_{13}$ (MPa)	75
Transverse tensile failure strain ε_{2T} (%)	0.55
In-plane shear failure strain γ_{12u} (%)	2.0

Table 3. Critical displacements (u_{crit}) and failure load (F_{crit}) of the double-notched specimens with different scales

Spec	Normal size		Notch-size scaling		Ply-level scaling	
	u_{crit} (mm)	F_{crit} (N)	u_{crit} (mm)	F_{crit} (N)	u_{crit} (mm)	F_{crit} (N)
1	0.641	7146.1	0.664	12418.6	0.493	17898.7
2	0.720	7415.8	0.670	13185.9	0.489	18275.0
3	0.639	7541.5	0.625	12183.4	0.533	19451.0
4	0.621	6696.5	0.660	11995.2	0.494	18533.8
5	0.678	8089.1				
Avg	0.656	7377.8	0.654	12445.8	0.502	18539.6
SD*	0.039	513.0	0.020	522.9	0.021	661.2
CV* (%)	5.9	6.9	3.1	4.2	4.1	3.6

*Avg: Average; SD: Standard deviation; CV: Coefficient of variation

Fig. 2 Failure of $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ specimens (a), notched-size scaled $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ specimen (b) and ply-level scaled $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ specimen (c)

Table 4. Failure criteria

Criterion	Formulations
Tsai-Wu	$F_i \sigma_i + F_{ij} \sigma_i \sigma_j \leq 1$
Christensen	Matrix failure: $\left(\frac{1}{Y_T} - \frac{1}{Y_C}\right)(\sigma_2 + \sigma_3) + \frac{1}{Y_T Y_C}(\sigma_2 + \sigma_3)^2 + \frac{1}{S_{12}^2}(\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2) + \frac{1}{S_{23}^2}(\sigma_{23}^2 - \sigma_2 \sigma_3) \leq 1$ Fibre failure: $-X_C \leq \sigma_1 \leq X_T$
MMF	Matrix failure: $\sigma_{VM}^2 + (C_m - T_m)I_1 - C_m T_m \leq 0$ Fibre failure: $\sigma_{1f}^2 + (C_f - T_f)\sigma_{1f} - C_f T_f \leq 0$
CDM	$Y_F = \frac{\partial E_D}{\partial d_F} \Big _{\sigma, d_F} = \frac{1}{2(1-d_F)^2} \left[\frac{\sigma_1^2}{E_1^0} - \sum_{i,j=1}^3 \left(\frac{\nu_{ij}^0}{E_i^0} + \frac{\nu_{ji}^0}{E_j^0} \right) \sigma_i \sigma_j \right],$ $Y_{d1} = \frac{\partial E_D}{\partial d_1} \Big _{\sigma, d_1} = \frac{1}{2(1-d_1)^2} \left(\frac{\sigma_2^2}{E_2^0} + \frac{\sigma_3^2}{E_3^0} \right),$ $Y_{d2} = \frac{\partial E_D}{\partial d_2} \Big _{\sigma, d_2} = \frac{1}{2(1-d_2)^2} \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}^2}{G_{12}^0} + \frac{\sigma_{23}^2}{G_{23}^0} + \frac{\sigma_{13}^2}{G_{13}^0} \right)$ Fiber failure : $d_F = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } Y_F < Y_{f1} \text{ when compression or } Y_F < Y_{f2} \text{ when tension} \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$ Matrix failure: $d'_i = \left\langle \sqrt{Y} - Y_{oi} \right\rangle_+ / Y_{ci}, \quad (i=1,2)$ $d_i = \begin{cases} d'_i, & \text{if } d'_i < 1 \text{ and } Y_{di} < Y_s \\ 1, & \text{if } d'_i \geq 1 \text{ or } Y_{di} \geq Y_s \end{cases}, \quad (i=1,2)$

Table 5. Cohesive properties of AS4/3501-6 composite material [6]

Material parameters	Values
Cohesive modulus E_0 (GPa)	4.0
Cohesive thickness h_0 (mm)	0.005
Cohesive normal strength S_n (MPa)	60

Cohesive shear strengths $S_s = S_t$ (MPa)	68
Mode I G_{Ic} (N/mm)	0.075
Modes II and III $G_{IIc} = G_{IIIc}$ (N/mm)	0.547

Fig. 3 Fiber modelling strategy for different failure theories: (a) traditional failure theories and (b) modified failure theories

Fig. 4 Boundary conditions and mesh of the FE models for the carbon/epoxy composite laminates: (a) $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate, (b) mesh and (c) cohesive elements at the interfaces

Fig. 5 Predicted load-displacement curves of the $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminates and comparison with the experiment

Fig. 6 Predicted failure patterns of the $[45/90/-45/0]_s$ laminate by the MChristensen criterion and comparison with the experiment (dark area in ply: fibre failure; grey area in ply: matrix failure; dark area at interfaces: delamination)

Fig. 7 Predicted load-displacement curves of the notch-size scaled laminate and comparison with the experiment

Fig. 8 Predicted load-displacement curves of the ply-level scaled laminate and comparison with the experiment

Fig. 9 Predicted failure patterns of the notch-size scaled laminate by MChristensen and comparison

with the experiment (dark area in ply: fibre failure; gray area in ply: matrix failure; dark area at interfaces: delamination)

Fig. 10 Predicted failure patterns of the ply-level scaled laminate and comparison with the experiment (dark area in ply: fiber failure; gray area in ply: matrix failure; dark area at interfaces: delamination)

Table 6. Summary of the percentage of strength reduction for scaling effects.

Methods	Notch-size scaling effect	Ply-level scaling effect
Experiment	15.65 %	37.18 %
Christensen	14.09 %	32.72 %
Tsai-Wu	14.45 %	33.11 %
MMF	13.97 %	33.82 %
CDM	10.23 %	28.87 %
MCDM	17.18 %	34.84 %
MChristensen	18.54 %	37.01 %

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